

HIGH STRAIN RATE EFFECT OF CARBON FIBER LAMINATES UNDER HYGROTHERMAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

With the widely application of composite materials in aerospace and other industrial fields, the influences of hygrothermal effects and high strain rate on impact mechanical properties of composites is becoming an important research problem in designing and evaluating advanced composites. Several researchers have found that water absorption by composites causes degradation of matrix dominated quasi-static properties. However, the investigation about the effect of high strain rate on impact mechanical properties of composites under hygrothermal environment is still relatively rare. In this paper, the impact mechanical performances of T300 carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin matrix composite laminates under hygrothermal circumstance and high strain rate are investigated using a Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB). First, both hygrothermal treated specimens and dry specimens are prepared. Second, impact mechanical behaviors of carbon fiber laminates under hygrothermal environment are studied using SHPB impact experiments. The results indicate that carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin matrix composite laminates have the strain rate sensitivity in the vertical direction, when the strain rate increased from 1500s^{-1} to 6000s^{-1} , the maximum engineering stress of the specimens increased nearly threefold. Also, hygrothermal treatment can improve the dynamic mechanical performance of this kind of material, the hygrothermal treated specimens exhibit higher dynamic compression strength perpendicular to the fiber ply, up to 12.45% compared to the dry specimens.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites have high specific strength\stiffness, fatigue resistance, corrosion resistance and other excellent mechanical properties. With the widely application of composite materials in aerospace and other industrial fields, the influences of hygrothermal effects and high strain rate on impact mechanical properties of composites is becoming an important research problem in designing and evaluating advanced composites.[1-3]

The split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) is widely used in studying the dynamic mechanical properties of composites materials. EI-Habak et al.[4] found that the compression strength of three different substrate (vinylester, polyester and epoxy groups) glass fiber laminate increase linearly with the strain rate when the strain rate changes within a range of 100s^{-1} to 1000s^{-1} , Gilat et al.[5] pointed out that the strain rate and ply angles have significant influences on the dynamic properties of the carbon fiber reinforced composite laminates. Meanwhile, Jedidi et al.[6] indicated that the shear properties of the composite laminate sharply declined in the hygrothermal environment for a long time

due to the destroy of the interfacial adhesion between resin matrix and fibers after water absorption. However, the investigation about the influences of high strain rate on impact mechanical properties of composites under hygrothermal environment is still relatively rare.

This paper studied the impact mechanical performance of composites under the condition of the hygrothermal and high strain rate. The results will reveal dynamic hygrothermal effects of composites.

2 COMPOSITE SPECIMEN

In this study, the ply material of the carbon fiber reinforced resin matrix composite laminates is CYCOM® 977-2A-37%-3KHTA-5H-280 prepreg cloth with 0.28mm in thickness and CYCOM® 977-2-35%-12KHTS-134 unidirectional prepreg tape with 0.134mm in thickness, which is produced by U.S. Cytec. The final composite laminates have 18 layers with a total the thickness of 3.884mm. The impact specimen is a cylinder with a diameter of 12mm and thickness of 3.884mm. The impact direction is along the thickness direction and perpendicular to the ply layer. All specimens are cut from one same laminate board. The ply conditions and mechanical parameters of the specimen are shown in Table 1.

Material	Compressive modulus warp/GPa	Compressive modulus weft/GPa	In-plane shear modulus/GPa	Poisson's ratio 0°/90°	Density/(g/cm ³)
M1	56.03(RT/dry)	55.6(RT/dry)	4.7	0.056	1.6
	59.29(70°C/wet)	59.7(70°C/wet)			
M2	119.4(RT/dry)	120.1(RT/dry)	5.13	0.3	1.6
	115.5(70°C/wet)	114.9(70°C/wet)			
Ply sequences		±45/0/±45/±45/0/±45/±45/0/0/±45/±45/0/±45/±45/0/±45			

Note*: 1.M1—977-2A-37%-3KHTA-5H-280; M2—977-2-35%-12KHTS-134;
 2. Wet = 70°C @ 80%RH to equilibrium;
 3. The underlined layers refer to M2—977-2-35%-12KHTS-134.

Table 1: Ply sequences and mechanical properties of ply materials

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

3.1 hygrothermal Treatment

The hygrothermal treatment on specimens was conducted according to HB7401-96 *Hygroscopic Experimental Methods for Resin-based Composite Laminates in hygrothermal Environment*. First, the specimens of the laminate were placed in a constant temperature oven at 70°C to obtain continuous drying, weighed regularly using the FA1004B millionth scale from Scientific Instrument Co., Shanghai till the loss of mass is no more than 0.02% everyday. Then the specimens reaching engineering dry state were placed in the automatic temperature box of 70°C, 80%RH to absorb water, also weighed regularly after cooled to room temperature, till the increase of mass is no more than 0.02% everyday. The water absorbent capacity of the specimens is calculated as follow:

$$W_i = \frac{G_i - G_d}{G_d} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where W_i , G_d , G_i are the absorbent capacity of the specimens, the mass in the engineering dry state and the mass after a period of time of absorption, respectively.

3.2 SHPB Experiment

High strain rate compression test was conducted on the SHPB device ($\varphi=19$) as shown in Figure 1. The basic principle of SHPB technology is described as follow: a short sample between two pressure bar is considered, acceleration pulse is generated using the impact of mass block or explosion, then the stress wave in the bar is monitored by means of the strain sensor on the radial surface of pressure bars, finally the impact load is obtained using the one-dimensional stress wave theory in an infinite cylindrical solid. When the specimens reach a dynamical balance, the strain and stress in the specimens are given by equation (2) to (5) [7, 8]:

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = \frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = \frac{C_0(\varepsilon_I - \varepsilon_R - \varepsilon_T)}{L_0} = -\frac{2C_0\varepsilon_R}{L_0} \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon = -\frac{2C_0}{L_0} \int_0^t \varepsilon_R(t) dt \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma = EA_1[\varepsilon_I + \varepsilon_R + \varepsilon_T] / 2A_2 = \frac{EA_1}{A_2} \varepsilon_T(t) \quad (4)$$

since

$$\varepsilon_I(t) + \varepsilon_R(t) = \varepsilon_T(t) \quad (5)$$

where ε_I , ε_R , ε_T are the incident, reflected and transmitted pulses, respectively. A_1 , A_2 , E , C_0 , L_0 are the cross-sectional area of the bars and the specimens, the Young's modulus, the wave velocity in the bars and the length of the specimens, respectively.

In this study, 60 impact tests at different strain rates by adjusting the driving air pressure (0.02MPa~0.09MPa) of the bullets were carried out on both the dry specimens and those with moisture absorption treatment.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of SHPB.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Effects of Hygrothermal Treatment

The desorption and absorption process for the composite specimens lasted for 6 days and 20 days, respectively. The average amount of water loss for a single specimen is about 0.18358% and the water absorption is 0.6253%. The desorption and absorption process of specimen No. 1 is presented in Figure 2. It is clear that the water desorption and absorption of carbon fiber laminate specimens have characteristics of two-stage process: In the beginning of desorption (absorption), the desorption (absorption) amount of the specimen is continuously increased, then gradually reaches a stable state and maintains for a while. then the laminate begins new desorption (absorption) process, and the desorption (absorption) amount and time present a linear relationship until the specimen reaches engineering dry state or moisture saturation.

The main reason for the above stated phenomenon is summarized as follows: First, the water molecules penetrate into the specimen through the gap among the material layers, cracks, pores etc. In this phase, the matrix plays a major role in the moisture absorption and the damage on the layer interface is tiny. As the moisture content increases, it will be more and more difficult for the water

molecules to penetrate and the specimen gradually reaches saturation. Second, the resin matrix after water erosion will be softened and a series of chemical phenomena will occur. Besides, the matrix will get postcured at high temperature and then combine with a number of hydrophilic groups, which is the phenomenon of “second absorption”. It is obvious that the water absorption characteristics of composite materials depend on the properties of the resin matrix and fiber, and their binding condition[9].

Figure 2: Dehydration and rehydration curve of carbon/epoxy composite specimens.

4.2 Effect of High Strain Rate

After finishing all the SHPB impact experiments, Figure 3 presents the typical engineering stress-strain curve about five representative strain rate groups. With the strain rate increasing, the linear part of the stress-strain curve gets longer in the initial load stage, which means that the elastic segment expands, the maximum engineering stress also increases; when the strain rate is greater than $3500s^{-1}$, the engineering stress-strain curve shows a significantly decrease after reaching the maximum stress value as shown in Figure 3, indicating that the specimen is damaged and the load capacity declines substantially. But when the strain rate is greater than $5000s^{-1}$, the stress-strain curve shows a tendency of slight increase after decrease, for which the possible reason is that the formation of the cracks on the specimens completes rapidly for the higher strain rate, and the specimen is divided into several parts, each of which is loading alone. From Figure 3 we can also find that the stress corresponding to the same strain for the composite specimen increases rapidly with the experimental strain rate rising.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curves at various strain rates

In Figure 4, the horizontal axis represents the strain rate, and the vertical axis represents the maximum engineering stress. Here, a power function is chosen for the curve fitting. The fitting formula for immersed specimens and dry specimens is formula (6) and (7), respectively:

$$\sigma = 0.60389 \dot{\epsilon}^{0.74704} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma = 0.42057 \dot{\epsilon}^{0.78411} \quad (7)$$

With the experimental strain rate increasing, the maximum engineering stress of the composite material increases. As the strain rate increases from 1500s^{-1} to 6000s^{-1} , the maximum engineering stress values of the composite specimens increases nearly three times. Thus, the mechanical properties of the composite materials are highly sensitive to the strain rate, both in dry state and hygrothermal environment. The fitting result shows that in the high strain rate impact test, the wet specimens exhibit higher maximum engineering stress values, up to 12.45% compared to the dry specimens.

In fact, numerous studies have shown that the moisture and high temperature will usually degrade the mechanical properties of the material³. However, an increase in impact strength of carbon fiber resin matrix composites after hygrothermal treatment at the high strain rate relative to the dry state specimens occurs due to absorption of moisture. Woldesenbet.E et al.[9] revealed that the material properties of the composite materials in hygrothermal environment are determined by both the plasticization of the matrix and the degradation of the fiber/matrix interface. In all experiments, the plasticization of the matrix is the dominant factor in high strain rate properties, and degradation of the fiber/matrix interface leads to the decrease of the enhancing effect of plasticization of the matrix, the higher water absorption rate of materials is, the worse the fiber-matrix interface will degrade.

For the water absorption and temperature given in this experiment, an increase in impact mechanical properties of the hygrothermal treated specimens occurs, which is very different from the quasi-static test, because of the more significant plasticization of the matrix compared with the degradation of the fiber/matrix interface.

Figure 4: Maximum stress-strain rate curves for different moisture conditions.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper studied the impact mechanical performance of composites under the condition of the hygrothermal and high strain rate. Some important conclusions are summarized as follow:

1. The carbon fiber reinforced resin matrix composite laminate specimens show the characteristics of two-stage in the process of desorption and absorption, and especially exist a phenomenon of secondary absorbent.

2. The carbon fiber reinforced resin matrix composite laminate has strong strain rate sensitivity in the vertical direction of the ply. The maximum stress of the composite material increases rapidly in the elastic section with the strain rate rising. When the strain rate increases from 1500s^{-1} to 6000s^{-1} , the maximum engineering stress of the composite specimen in the hygrothermal treatment group and the control group increases nearly threefold.

3. The wet specimens exhibit higher dynamic compression strength perpendicular to the fiber ply, up to 12.45% compared to the dry specimens in high strain rate impact tests and this phenomenon is more significant when the strain rate is relatively low.

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